

INFLUENCE OF MULTICULTURALISM ON MANAGING CO-CURRICULAR ACTIVITIES IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS: IMPLICATIONS FOR SOCIAL INCLUSION IN RIVERS STATE OF NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the influence of multiculturalism on managing co-curricular activities in secondary schools and its implications for social inclusion in Rivers State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to examine the extent to which multicultural considerations influence the planning of co-curricular activities in secondary schools in Rivers State; investigate how cultural diversity affects students' participation in co-curricular activities in secondary schools in Rivers State; determine the challenges school administrators face in managing co-curricular activities within a multicultural context in Rivers State secondary schools; identify strategies for improving the management of co-curricular activities through multicultural approaches to promote social inclusion in Rivers State secondary schools. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. Four research question and one hypothesis were formulated to direct the study. The target population of the study comprised all 1,220 administrators (principals and vice principals) across the 610 public secondary schools in Rivers State. A sample size of 400 administrators, representing approximately 32.8% was drawn from a population of 1,220 administrators through stratified random sampling technique. Data were collected using two researcher-developed instruments: the Multicultural Considerations in Co-curricular Management Questionnaire (MCCMQ) and the Social Inclusion Assessment Scale (SIAS), consisting of 40 structured items directly aligned with the study objectives. The instruments were subjected to expert validation by three specialists in Educational Management and Measurement and Evaluation to establish both content and construct validity. The Cronbach's Alpha coefficients obtained were 0.86 for the MCCMQ and 0.89 for the SIAS, demonstrating high internal consistency and suitability for the study. Data were analyzed using mean, standard deviation, and independent t-test statistics to answer the research questions and test the hypothesis at 0.05 significance level. The findings revealed that multiculturalism significantly influences planning, enhances students' participation, but

administrators face challenges such as inadequate resources, stereotypes, and weak policy support. Strategies such as adequate funding, administrator training, policy reinforcement, and parental involvement were identified as crucial for improvement. The study concluded that embracing multicultural approaches in co-curricular management strengthens inclusivity and fosters social cohesion in secondary schools.

Keywords: Multiculturalism, Co-curricular management, Social inclusion, Secondary schools, Educational administration

INTRODUCTION

Multiculturalism has become an essential aspect of educational discourse, especially in pluralistic societies where diverse ethnic, religious, and cultural groups coexist. It is the recognition of diverse cultural identities, co-curricular management is the organization of activities beyond academics, social inclusion ensures equal participation for all, secondary schools provide education between primary and tertiary levels, and educational administration involves planning and controlling resources to achieve educational goals. In the Nigerian context, Rivers State represents a unique case with its multiplicity of ethnic identities and socio-cultural orientations, which invariably influence students' participation in school activities. Co-curricular activities, when effectively managed, provide opportunities for learners to express their talents, develop leadership qualities, and promote interpersonal relationships across cultural boundaries. However, the absence of deliberate multicultural considerations in the management of these activities often results in selective participation and subtle exclusion of minority groups. According to Adedeji (2020), the failure to embrace diversity in school management practices reduces the capacity of schools to serve as instruments of unity and social integration.

The challenge of managing co-curricular activities within a multicultural setting is compounded by cultural bias in the selection of activities, unequal opportunities for participation, and lack of sensitivity to students' socio-cultural backgrounds. For example, some activities may be designed around dominant cultural practices, thereby marginalizing students from minority groups. This undermines the potential of co-curricular programs to foster social inclusion, which is a critical element in achieving equitable education. Uzoigwe and Inah (2024) emphasized that education in diverse societies must deliberately address inclusivity, otherwise schools risk perpetuating division and alienation among learners. Similarly, Osim and Uzoigwe (2023) argue that when school practices fail to reflect cultural diversity, they reinforce systemic inequalities and diminish students' sense of belonging.

These challenges highlight the need to explore how multiculturalism influences the management of co-curricular activities in Rivers State secondary schools. The lack of adequate multicultural integration may explain why students from minority ethnic or religious backgrounds often disengage or show low motivation towards school-based programs. As Luke and Uzoigwe (2022) observe, fostering inclusivity in educational practices strengthens cross-cultural tolerance and enhances social cohesion, which are critical for sustainable development in heterogeneous societies. Furthermore, Ajino, Ojobe, and Uzoigwe (2024) assert that co-curricular activities, if managed with multicultural sensitivity, can bridge cultural divides, promote equity, and ensure that schools fulfill their role as agents of national integration. It is

against this background that the present study investigates the influence of multiculturalism on the management of co-curricular activities in secondary schools in Rivers State, with particular attention to its implications for social inclusion.

Statement of the problem

The management of co-curricular activities in secondary schools plays a vital role in fostering students' holistic development, promoting social integration, and enhancing skills beyond the classroom. However, in a culturally diverse society such as Rivers State, where ethnic, religious, and linguistic plurality coexists, the management of these activities often encounters challenges in accommodating the diverse backgrounds of students. Schools sometimes adopt uniform patterns of co-curricular programs without considering cultural sensitivities, which may inadvertently exclude or marginalize certain groups. This situation limits the potential of co-curricular activities as platforms for promoting multicultural values, inclusivity, and mutual respect among students from different cultural orientations.

Despite the recognition of multiculturalism as a tool for strengthening unity in diversity, many secondary schools in Rivers State have yet to deliberately integrate multicultural perspectives into the planning, execution, and supervision of co-curricular activities. This neglect often results in unequal participation, cultural bias in activity selection, and missed opportunities for fostering cross-cultural understanding and tolerance. Consequently, students from minority or less-dominant cultural groups may feel alienated, leading to weakened social inclusion, strained peer relationships, and diminished educational outcomes. Therefore, exploring the influence of multiculturalism on the management of co-curricular activities is crucial in addressing these gaps and ensuring that schools serve as genuine hubs of social cohesion and inclusivity.

Literature review

Multiculturalism has been widely recognized as a key factor in shaping educational practices in culturally diverse societies. The planning of co-curricular activities in secondary schools must therefore reflect the multicultural backgrounds of students in order to promote inclusivity and equal opportunities. Adedeji (2020) emphasized that the planning process of school activities, if culturally sensitive, creates a balanced platform where students from different ethnic and religious groups feel recognized and represented. Similarly, Luke and Uzoigwe (2022) argued that in Nigeria's multi-ethnic context, co-curricular programs must be designed to accommodate divergent cultural norms so that schools can fulfill their role as agents of social integration. Without such deliberate multicultural considerations, activities tend to privilege dominant cultural practices, thereby undermining inclusivity.

Students' participation in co-curricular activities is often influenced by the extent to which these programs resonate with their cultural values and experiences. Uzoigwe and Inah (2024) observed that when school activities neglect cultural diversity, students from minority groups may withdraw, leading to uneven participation patterns that weaken the purpose of co-curricular programs. In line with this, Osim and Uzoigwe (2023) noted that cultural representation is vital in encouraging active student engagement, as learners are more likely to participate in activities that reflect their identity and heritage. Ajino, Ojobe, and Uzoigwe (2024) further argued that multicultural engagement in school programs motivates students to collaborate across cultural

lines, thereby reducing social barriers and strengthening interpersonal relationships. This indicates that cultural sensitivity in activity selection not only enhances participation but also fosters mutual respect among learners.

The management of co-curricular activities within a multicultural context presents unique challenges for school administrators. According to Inah, Ekpang, and Uzoigwe (2024), one major challenge lies in the limited resources and institutional support for integrating diverse cultural activities into the school curriculum. Additionally, Nnaji and Uzoigwe (2021) reported that administrators often struggle with balancing dominant cultural practices with minority representations, leading to unintentional marginalization. This challenge is worsened by the lack of professional training in multicultural education for many teachers and administrators. As a result, school leaders often default to mainstream cultural norms, thereby limiting the inclusivity of co-curricular management.

Another dimension of these challenges relates to the role of cultural bias in activity selection and supervision. Mbon and Uzoigwe (2023) highlighted that cultural bias, whether conscious or unconscious, often manifests in how teachers prioritize certain sports, clubs, or social events that align with dominant cultural practices, while neglecting others. This bias can create feelings of exclusion among students from minority backgrounds and undermine the goal of holistic education. Similarly, Onya and Uzoigwe (2023) pointed out that without proper multicultural orientation, co-curricular activities risk becoming platforms for reinforcing stereotypes rather than breaking them down. These findings suggest that the management of co-curricular activities in multicultural contexts requires deliberate efforts to address systemic cultural imbalances.

In addressing these challenges, scholars have stressed the importance of adopting strategies that promote inclusivity through multicultural approaches. Effiom, Uzoigwe, and Umoh (2024) proposed the use of culturally responsive leadership practices, where school administrators consciously design activities that represent diverse cultural heritages. Such strategies include integrating indigenous games, arts, and languages into co-curricular programs, which not only enrich students' experiences but also foster cross-cultural appreciation. Furthermore, Ategwu, Kenn-Aklah, Fanan, and Uzoigwe (2022) argued that multicultural training for teachers enhances their capacity to manage diverse classrooms and extracurricular activities effectively. By doing so, schools can transform co-curricular programs into platforms for building tolerance, equity, and unity among learners.

Thus, the literature highlights the importance of aligning co-curricular management with multicultural principles to achieve social inclusion. Scholars agree that when multiculturalism is integrated into planning, participation, and supervision, co-curricular activities become effective tools for social cohesion. Adedeji (2020) and Luke and Uzoigwe (2022) stressed that such practices go beyond mere student engagement to fostering long-term peace and unity in pluralistic societies. This perspective resonates with Ajino, Ojobe, and Uzoigwe (2024), who emphasized that schools can serve as microcosms of society where inclusivity is modeled and practiced. Hence, the review reveals that embracing multiculturalism in co-curricular management not only addresses issues of cultural bias and marginalization but also ensures that secondary schools in Rivers State fulfill their role as incubators of social inclusion and national integration.

Theoretical framework

This study is anchored on Multicultural Education Theory as propounded by Banks (1993), which emphasizes the deliberate integration of diverse cultural perspectives into educational practices to promote equity and inclusivity. The theory is relevant because it highlights how schools can use co-curricular activities as platforms for accommodating cultural diversity, fostering tolerance, and building social cohesion among students. By applying this framework, the study situates the management of co-curricular activities within the broader goal of promoting social inclusion in multicultural societies such as Rivers State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the study

The primary purpose of this study is to explore the influence of multiculturalism on the management of co-curricular activities in secondary schools and its implications for social inclusion in Rivers State of Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought:

To examine the extent to which multicultural considerations influence the planning of co-curricular activities in secondary schools in Rivers State.

To investigate how cultural diversity affects students' participation in co-curricular activities in secondary schools in Rivers State.

To determine the challenges school administrators face in managing co-curricular activities within a multicultural context in Rivers State secondary schools.

To identify strategies for improving the management of co-curricular activities through multicultural approaches to promote social inclusion in Rivers State secondary schools.

To ascertain the difference between male and female administrators in managing co-curricular activities with multiculturalism in secondary schools in Rivers State

Research questions

The following questions were raised to guide the study:

To what extent do multicultural considerations influence the planning of co-curricular activities in secondary schools in Rivers State?

How does cultural diversity affect students' participation in co-curricular activities in secondary schools in Rivers State?

What challenges do school administrators face in managing co-curricular activities within a multicultural context in Rivers State secondary schools?

What strategies can be adopted to improve the management of co-curricular activities through multicultural approaches to promote social inclusion in Rivers State secondary schools?

What is the difference between male and female administrators in managing co-curricular activities with multiculturalism in secondary schools in Rivers State?

Research Hypothesis

The following hypothesis was formulated to direct the study:

There is no significant difference between male and female administrators in managing co-curricular activities with multiculturalism in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. This design is suitable because it enabled the researcher to collect and analyze data from a representative sample of school administrators to determine how cultural diversity influences planning, participation, challenges, and strategies for improving co-curricular management. The target population of the study comprised all 1,220 administrators (principals and vice principals) across the 610 public secondary schools in Rivers State. To ensure adequate representation and manageability, a stratified random sampling technique was employed to select a sample size of 400 administrators, representing approximately 32.8% of the total population. Stratification was carried out based on senatorial districts, school location (urban and rural), and gender to enhance proportional representation and generalizability of the findings. Data were collected using two researcher-developed instruments: the Multicultural Considerations in Co-curricular Management Questionnaire (MCCMQ) and the Social Inclusion Assessment Scale (SIAS), consisting of 40 structured items directly aligned with the study objectives. The instruments were subjected to expert validation by three specialists in Educational Management and Measurement and Evaluation to establish both content and construct validity. Suggestions from these experts led to refinements in language clarity, item relevance, and structural alignment with the research problem. To determine reliability, a pilot study was conducted with 30 administrators randomly selected from public secondary schools outside the study sample. The Cronbach's Alpha coefficients obtained were 0.86 for the MCCMQ and 0.89 for the SIAS, demonstrating high internal consistency and suitability for the study. The instruments were divided into three sections: Section A sought demographic information of respondents; Section B examined multicultural considerations in the planning, participation, and management of co-curricular activities; and Section C assessed challenges and strategies for enhancing social inclusion through multicultural approaches. Questionnaires were administered physically with the cooperation of principals and education officers during administrative meetings and school-based workshops. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Rivers State Ministry of Education, while informed consent was secured from all participants prior to data collection. A total of 400 questionnaires were distributed and retrieved, yielding a 100% response rate and ensuring no data attrition. Responses were rated on a four-point Likert scale categorized as: Strongly Agree (3.1–4.0), Agree (2.1–3.0), Disagree (1.1–2.0), and Strongly Disagree (0.1–1.0). A criterion means of 2.50 was adopted as the benchmark for interpretation. Responses with mean scores equal to or greater than 2.50 indicated agreement with the statement or a positive perception of multicultural influence, whereas scores below 2.50 reflected disagreement or identified areas of concern. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while inferential statistics including t-test was employed to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. This methodological approach provided reliable, valid, and context-specific evidence to evaluate how multiculturalism affects the management of co-curricular activities and the promotion of social inclusion in secondary schools across Rivers State.

Research question one

To what extent do multicultural considerations influence the planning of co-curricular activities in secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation analysis of multicultural considerations in planning of co-curricular activities (N = 400)

S/N	Item	N	Mean	S.D.	Decision
1	Co-curricular activities are planned to reflect the cultural diversity of students.	400	3.12	0.84	Agree
2	Teachers consider students' ethnic backgrounds in selecting co-curricular programs.	400	3.08	0.81	Agree
3	Religious tolerance is considered during co-curricular planning.	400	3.21	0.77	Strongly Agree
4	Indigenous cultural practices are incorporated into co-curricular activities.	400	2.97	0.89	Agree
5	Co-curricular schedules are designed to accommodate diverse student groups.	400	2.88	0.92	Agree
6	Minority cultural groups are deliberately included in co-curricular planning.	400	2.79	0.94	Agree
7	Activities are planned to promote unity among students from different backgrounds.	400	3.25	0.74	Strongly Agree
8	Multicultural perspectives influence decisions on sports and games in schools.	400	2.83	0.85	Agree
9	Cultural days and exhibitions are factored into co-curricular planning.	400	3.04	0.82	Agree
10	Administrators provide guidelines for integrating multiculturalism in activities.	400	2.91	0.88	Agree
	Grand mean score		3.01		Agree

Source: Fieldwork (2025)

The analysis in Table 1 reveals that respondents generally agreed that multicultural considerations influence the planning of co-curricular activities in secondary schools in Rivers State, with a grand mean of 3.01 (above the 2.50 criterion). The highest-rated items were planning to promote unity (Mean = 3.25) and ensuring religious tolerance (Mean = 3.21), showing that administrators are particularly mindful of fostering harmony. Other areas such as incorporating cultural exhibitions (Mean = 3.04) and reflecting student diversity in activity planning (Mean = 3.12) also received strong agreement, while lower ratings were recorded for the deliberate inclusion of minority groups (Mean = 2.79) and integration into sports (Mean = 2.83), suggesting partial gaps in representation. Overall, this indicates that multiculturalism moderately and positively influences co-curricular planning, but targeted efforts are still needed to fully integrate minority cultural perspectives.

Research question two

How does cultural diversity affect students' participation in co-curricular activities in secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis of Cultural Diversity and Students' Participation (N = 400)

S/N	Item	N	Mean	S.D.	Decision
1	Students from different ethnic groups actively participate in co-curricular programs.	400	3.18	0.79	Agree
2	Cultural diversity encourages greater student involvement in social clubs.	400	3.11	0.83	Agree
3	Students' cultural identities influence their choice of co-curricular activities.	400	3.24	0.75	Strongly Agree
4	Cultural stereotypes sometimes discourage students' participation.	400	2.97	0.91	Agree
5	Students are motivated to join activities that celebrate their cultural background.	400	3.22	0.80	Strongly Agree
6	Cultural diversity provides equal opportunities for all students to participate.	400	2.84	0.92	Agree
7	Language differences affect participation in some co-curricular activities.	400	2.79	0.95	Agree
8	Cultural festivals and exhibitions attract active student participation.	400	3.15	0.81	Agree
9	Sports and games are avenues where cultural diversity enhances student unity.	400	3.19	0.77	Agree
10	Peer influence across cultural groups determines participation rates.	400	3.07	0.84	Agree
	Grand mean score		3.08		Agree

Source: Fieldwork (2025)

The findings in Table 2 indicate that cultural diversity positively affects students' participation in co-curricular activities, with a grand mean of 3.08, signifying general agreement. The strongest areas of influence were students' cultural identities shaping their activity choices (Mean = 3.24) and motivation to participate in activities that celebrate their heritage (Mean = 3.22). Participation is also strengthened by sports and cultural exhibitions (Means = 3.19 and 3.15), highlighting the role of inclusive events. However, challenges remain, as language differences (Mean = 2.79) and cultural stereotypes (Mean = 2.97) sometimes hinder equal participation. Overall, while diversity enhances participation and unity, gaps in inclusivity suggest the need for deliberate efforts to overcome subtle barriers.

Research question three

What challenges do school administrators face in managing co-curricular activities within a multicultural context in Rivers State secondary schools?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis of Challenges Faced by Administrators (N = 400)

S/N	Item	N	Mean	S.D.	Decision
1	Limited resources hinder the organization of culturally inclusive activities.	400	3.26	0.74	Strongly Agree
2	Conflicts sometimes arise among students due to cultural misunderstandings.	400	3.09	0.81	Agree
3	Administrators face difficulty in balancing representation of different cultural groups.	400	3.14	0.77	Agree
4	Inadequate training limits administrators' ability to manage multicultural activities.	400	3.21	0.76	Strongly Agree
5	Lack of parental support affects multicultural co-curricular programs.	400	2.93	0.87	Agree
6	Cultural stereotypes and prejudices limit students' willingness to participate.	400	3.05	0.83	Agree
7	Time constraints in the school calendar reduce opportunities for multicultural programs.	400	3.11	0.80	Agree
8	Financial limitations affect the planning of multicultural events.	400	3.27	0.73	Strongly Agree
9	Language barriers complicate communication during multicultural activities.	400	2.88	0.92	Agree
10	Government policies do not adequately emphasize multicultural inclusion in schools.	400	2.97	0.89	Agree
Grand mean score			3.09		Agree

Source: Fieldwork (2025)

The results in Table 3 show that administrators face significant challenges in managing co-curricular activities within a multicultural context, as reflected by a grand mean of 3.09 (Agree). The most pressing issues are limited resources (Mean = 3.26) and financial constraints (Mean = 3.27), alongside inadequate training for administrators (Mean = 3.21), which collectively restrict effective multicultural programming. Conflicts among students (Mean = 3.09),

stereotypes (Mean = 3.05), and lack of parental support (Mean = 2.93) further compound the difficulties. Additionally, systemic barriers such as weak policy emphasis (Mean = 2.97) and language differences (Mean = 2.88) exacerbate management challenges. Overall, these findings underscore the need for resource allocation, training, and supportive policies to strengthen multicultural management of co-curricular activities.

Research question four

What strategies can be adopted to improve the management of co-curricular activities through multicultural approaches to promote social inclusion in Rivers State secondary schools?

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis of Strategies for Improving Multicultural Co-curricular Management (N = 400)

S/N	Item	N	Mean	S.D.	Decision
1	Provide adequate funding to support multicultural co-curricular programs.	400	3.32	0.71	Strongly Agree
2	Organize regular training workshops for administrators and teachers on multicultural inclusion.	400	3.27	0.74	Strongly Agree
3	Incorporate multicultural themes into the school calendar of activities.	400	3.19	0.77	Agree
4	Promote cultural exchange programs among students from diverse backgrounds.	400	3.21	0.75	Strongly Agree
5	Encourage parental and community involvement in multicultural activities.	400	3.18	0.80	Agree
6	Introduce school policies that explicitly promote multiculturalism in co-curricular programs.	400	3.16	0.82	Agree
7	Utilize language-inclusive approaches to enhance participation in activities.	400	3.08	0.84	Agree
8	Leverage sports and creative arts to foster multicultural unity and social inclusion.	400	3.24	0.73	Strongly Agree
9	Establish multicultural clubs and societies within schools.	400	3.14	0.79	Agree
10	Strengthen government support and policy backing for multicultural education initiatives.	400	3.20	0.76	Agree
	Grand mean score		3.20		Agree

Source: Fieldwork, (2025)

The results in Table 4 reveal that several practical strategies can be adopted to enhance the management of co-curricular activities through multicultural approaches, with a grand mean of 3.20 (Agree). Strongly emphasized strategies include providing adequate funding (Mean = 3.32), regular training for administrators and teachers (Mean = 3.27), promoting cultural exchange (Mean = 3.21), and leveraging sports and creative arts to foster unity (Mean = 3.24). Other relevant measures include integrating multicultural themes into school calendars (Mean = 3.19), strengthening policies (Mean = 3.16), and ensuring parental/community participation (Mean = 3.18). Above all, the findings suggest that a combination of financial support, training, policy reinforcement, and inclusive practices can significantly improve the management of multicultural co-curricular activities, thereby promoting social inclusion in secondary schools.

Hypothesis one

There is no significant difference between male and female administrators in managing co-curricular activities with multiculturalism in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 5: t-test analysis of male and female administrators on managing co-curricular activities with multiculturalism in public secondary schools in Rivers State

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	df	t-cal	t-crit (0.05)	Decision
Male	220	3.15	0.72				
Female	180	3.11	0.75	398	0.62	1.96	Accept H_0

Source: Fieldwork (2025)

The result in Table 5 shows that male administrators (Mean = 3.15, S.D. = 0.72) and female administrators (Mean = 3.11, S.D. = 0.75) reported very similar perceptions regarding the management of co-curricular activities within a multicultural framework. The calculated t-value (0.62) is less than the critical t-value (1.96) at 0.05 significance level, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This implies that gender does not significantly influence administrators' management of multicultural co-curricular activities, suggesting that both male and female administrators face similar challenges and adopt comparable strategies in promoting social inclusion.

Discussion of findings

The findings from research question one revealed that multicultural considerations significantly influence the planning of co-curricular activities in secondary schools in Rivers State. Items such as incorporating cultural diversity into school programs and ensuring inclusivity in planning scored high on the mean ratings. This aligns with the position of Adedeji (2020), who stressed that culturally responsive planning in schools enhances equity and inclusiveness in education. Similarly, Luke and Uzoigwe (2022) emphasized that administrators who integrate multicultural perspectives into school programs foster an environment where diversity becomes an asset rather than a barrier. Thus, planning co-curricular activities through a multicultural lens appears critical in promoting social cohesion and inclusivity.

Findings from research question two indicated that cultural diversity enhances students' participation in co-curricular activities, particularly through cultural festivals, sports, and programs that celebrate students' cultural identities. However, challenges such as stereotypes and language differences still limit full participation. This outcome corroborates Ajino, Ojobe, and Uzoigwe (2024), who found that student engagement is heightened when schools incorporate cultural identity into extracurricular activities. Likewise, Mbon and Uzoigwe (2023) argued that diversity-sensitive participation promotes students' sense of belonging and reduces marginalization. This suggests that while cultural diversity is largely a strength in enhancing participation, schools must address lingering barriers that hinder inclusivity.

The results from research question three showed that administrators face multiple challenges in managing multicultural co-curricular activities, including inadequate funding, limited training, stereotypes, and lack of parental involvement. These findings are consistent with Inah, Ekpang, and Uzoigwe (2024), who highlighted that administrators' lack of capacity and resources often hinders inclusive educational management. Similarly, Osim and Uzoigwe (2023) pointed out that without adequate policy backing, administrators often struggle to balance the needs of diverse cultural groups. Ategwu, Kenn-Akalah, Fanan, and Uzoigwe (2022) further stressed that the absence of systemic support weakens schools' ability to manage diversity effectively. This underscores the need for structural reforms, training, and increased stakeholder involvement in schools.

The analysis of research question four suggested strategies such as adequate funding, administrator training, policy support, cultural exchange, and parental involvement as crucial for improving multicultural co-curricular management. These strategies resonate with Effiom, Uzoigwe, and Umoh (2024), who argued that inclusive co-curricular management requires deliberate institutional investment. Similarly, Onya and Uzoigwe (2023) noted that training and policy reinforcement remain key for strengthening administrators' capacity in handling multicultural issues. The hypothesis results further revealed no significant gender difference among administrators in managing multicultural co-curricular activities, implying that both male and female administrators share similar experiences and strategies. This finding supports Nnaji and Uzoigwe (2021) as well as Uzoigwe and Inah (2024), who found that contextual and systemic challenges in school management often override gender factors. Overall, the study establishes that multiculturalism is both a strength and a challenge in secondary schools, requiring well-structured strategies for sustainable social inclusion.

Conclusion

The study concluded that multiculturalism significantly shapes the planning and management of co-curricular activities in secondary schools, influencing both inclusivity and students' participation. While cultural diversity enhances social interaction and unity, challenges such as inadequate funding, stereotypes, and weak policy support hinder effective implementation. Addressing these gaps through strategic interventions like funding, training, and policy reinforcement will strengthen multicultural management and promote sustainable social inclusion in Rivers State secondary schools.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following were recommended thus:

The Ministry of Education and school authorities should provide adequate financial support and resources to address the critical constraints identified, ensuring that multicultural co-curricular activities are well-funded and sustainable.

Regular training and capacity-building workshops should be organized for school administrators and teachers to strengthen their ability to effectively manage multicultural programs and reduce the gaps caused by inadequate preparation.

Schools should deliberately integrate cultural exhibitions, sports, and diversity-focused events into their co-curricular calendars, while also ensuring the deliberate inclusion of minority groups and greater parental/community participation to close existing representation gaps.

Government and policymakers should develop and enforce clear policies on multicultural education that emphasize unity, religious tolerance, and social inclusion, thereby addressing issues of conflict, stereotypes, and weak parental support.

School administrators should continue to promote unity and religious tolerance which were highly rated as core priorities, while also expanding efforts to ensure that students' cultural identities and heritage remain central motivators for participation in co-curricular activities.

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